

BIOBASED MATERIALS: POTENTIALS AND OBSTACLES FOR STRUCTURE, STRENGTH AND PERFORMANCE OF CELLULOSE FIBRES AND THEIR COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Biobased materials are becoming of increasing interest as potential structural materials for the future. A useful concept in this context is the fibre reinforcement of materials by stiff and strong fibres. The bio-resources can contribute with cellulose fibres and (bio) polymers from hemicelluloses. This offers the potential for stiff and strong biocomposite materials, but these have some limitations and obstacles to full performance. The focus will be on the structure and strength of cellulose fibres and the mechanical performance of composites.

2 Cellulose Fibres

2.1 Structure

The cellulose is chemically based on the polysaccharide $(C_6H_{10}O_5)_n$, with molecular weight of 162. Practical cellulose fibres have typically 60-70% cellulose, the rest being hemicelluloses and lignin, [1]. Basically the cellulose has a crystalline structure (monoclinic) with unit cell dimensions of about 1 nm x 0.8 nm x 0.8 nm. In fibres the cellulose is partly crystalline and partly amorphous. The crystallinity for cellulose fibres derived from flax and hemp plants are typically about 90%, [2]. The theoretical properties for fully crystalline, pure cellulose can be calculated from the crystal structure and potential energy models for the bonding between the atoms. The theoretical maximum values are: density 1.64 g/cm³, stiffness 120 GPa, strength 15,000 MPa, see fig.1.

Fig. 1. Cellulose structure and properties.

The practical, experimentally derived values for cellulose fibres from e.g. flax and hemp plants, are density 1.5 g/cm³, stiffness 50-70 GPa, strength 600-900 MPa. For stiffness practical values are rather close to the theoretical value, so some potential still exists for improvement, for strength the practical values are significantly lower than the theoretical values and thus a large potential exists for improvement, but this is met with some obstacles, as described in the following sections.

2.2 Defects

The cellulose fibres, in general, contain defects, even in the as-grown condition. This initial defect type and content has not been established. The defects are typically disorder in the otherwise crystalline structure, and they are called kink bands or dislocations. The defects are normally observed by (optical) microscopy and quantified by the

number density of defects. It is expected that the (potential) effects of defects, on e.g. stiffness and strength, will be governed by the volume content of defects, and related studies are in progress. It is expected and observed, qualitatively, that processing of fibres, when converting plants to yarns, will have a damaging / defect generating effect on the fibres, see fig.2.

Fig. 2. Defects in flax cellulose fibres, caused by processing. The Green fibres (top picture) have formally no processing ($N = 0$), the Stem fibres (middle picture) have been processed through 1 step, retting ($N = 1$), and the Noils fibres (bottom picture) have been processed through two steps, retting + scutching ($N = 2$).

Fig. 3. Fibre bundle strength for flax fibres and hemp fibres, after a series of processing steps, from zero to five steps.

A study has been made [3], where it is assumed that each processing step has a similar effect in generating defects in the fibres. A range of flax and hemp fibres have been given processing steps from zero to 5. The chemical composition remained in practice unchanged at about 70%, and the crystallinity of cellulose remained unchanged at the level of 90-95%. The fibre bundle (yarn) strengths have been measured, and the strength values decrease monotonically, see fig.3, with an exponential decay, giving a strength decrease of about 25% per processing step. The processing from plant to yarn is an unavoidable chain of process steps to obtain useful fibres (performs) for composites, so this chain of processes is an obstacle to high strength. The potential action will be to reduce the number of steps and attempt to make individual steps as mild as possible in terms of defect generation. The potential processing types include chemical, biological and mechanical treatments.

3 Composite Performance

Composites made from cellulose fibres must follow the same rules as other composites in order to achieve good mechanical properties. Therefore, the aim is to use high fibre content, good fibre alignment and ensure low porosity in the composite. The cellulose fibres present some difficulties in this

respect, caused by their non-circular cross section, their non constant cross sectional area and their branching of individual fibre elements. This is in contrast to e.g. glass fibres with their circular, constant cross section and their straightness. To achieve high fibre volume fraction in a composite, a good packing capability is needed, experiments show that glass fibres in unidirectional configuration can be packed to about 70 %, while cellulose fibres in unidirectional configuration can be packed to 55-60%. For random fibre orientation configurations the values are 55% and 40-45%, respectively. If higher fibre contents are aimed at, the correspondingly lower matrix content will not be enough to fill the space between the optimally packed fibres, and this will lead to the presence of structural (unavoidable) porosity in the final composite, [4].

Fig. 4. Volumetric composition for composites, with fibre density larger than matrix density (cellulose density 1.5 g/cm^3 , matrix density 1.1 g/cm^3), limited packing ability of fibres, and structural porosity. The volume fractions for fibres (red curve), for matrix (blue curve) and for porosity (green curve) are plotted versus weight fraction of fibres. At the (transition) fibre weight fraction of ca 0.57 the packing of fibres is maximum, and the fibre volume fraction stays constant for higher fibre weight fractions, this causes the (structural) porosity to develop and increase.

This porosity is over and above any porosity in the matrix, caused by e.g. the processing of the composite. This situation defines a **maximum fibre**

volume fraction, at which the matrix content is just sufficient to avoid structural porosity, see fig.4. This maximum fibre volume fraction corresponds to a transition fibre **weight** fraction, beyond which structural porosity develops. A model has been established for the effect of fibre content and porosity content on the density and stiffness of the resulting composite, [4, 5]. This shows maximum values for density and stiffness at the transition fibre weight fraction, thus indicating an optimal combination of fibre content and porosity content, see fig.5. This model elucidates the potential for cellulose fibre composites in terms of stiffness (and strength), but also defines the limit to stiffness and strength. The obstacles are the moderate packing capability of the cellulose fibres, and improvements should be focused on improving the uniformity of morphology of cellulose fibres.

Fig. 5. Composite stiffness for jute fibre / polypropylene composites with 2-D random fibre orientation distribution. Fibre density is 1.52 g/cm^3 , matrix density 0.91 g/cm^3 , transition fibre **weight** fraction is 0.49, corresponding to maximum fibre **volume** fraction of 0.34, the maximum composite stiffness is obtained at this fibre fraction. Stiffness is plotted versus fibre weight fraction (calculated curve), and the experimental data are shown as circular points.

4 Status and Future

The present situation for cellulose fibres is for **stiffness: theoretical value 120 GPa, practical value 60-80 GPa, for strength: theoretical 15,000 MPa, practical value 600-900 MPa, cellulose**

crystallinity about 90%. The processing induced defects reduce fibre bundle strength by about 25% per processing step. Packing capability of cellulose fibres (unidirectional) is 55-60%. Maximum composite properties are obtained at a limiting fibre volume fraction, in combination with no structural porosity, see fig.6. The future approach should be aimed at (i) fibres with higher cellulose content and higher crystallinity, (ii) improved processing of cellulose fibres causing reduced defect content, (iii) developing cellulose fibres with uniform morphology in order to give better packing of fibres and thus higher maximum fibre volume fraction in composites, (iv) the potential use of nano scale crystalline cellulose fibrils leading to very high inherent stiffness and strength of fibres.

Cellulosic fibres and their composites

Fibre strength	max.	5000 - 10,000 MPa
	practical	600 - 900 MPa
Fibre stiffness	max.	ca 120 GPa
	practical	60 - 80 GPa

Cellulose crystallinity (plant fibre based) ca 90 %

Processing induced defects:

defects reduce fibre strength,
reduction is ca 25 % per processing step

Packing of cellulosic fibres to volume fraction max. 0.4 - 0.6:

this gives max. fibre volume fraction,
and related structural porosity

Max. obtainable **composite properties** (density, stiffness,)
at limiting max. fibre volume fraction

References

- [1] H.Lilholt, J.M. Lawther "Natural organic fibres". In *Comprehensive Composite Materials* (6 vols). Eds. A. Kelly and C. Zweben. Elsevier Science. Vol. 1, chap. 10, pp. 303-325, 2000.
- [2] A. Thygesen, J. Oddershede, H. Lilholt, A.B.Thomsen, K. Ståhl "On the determination of crystallinity and cellulose content in plant fibres". *Cellulose*, vol 12, pp 563-576, 2005.
- [3] A.Thygesen, B.Madsen, A.B.Bjerre, H.Lilholt "Cellulosic fibres: effect of processing on fibre bundle strength". Accepted for *J. Natural Fibres*, 2011.
- [4] B. Madsen, A. Thygesen, H. Lilholt "Plant fibre composites – porosity and volumetric interaction". *Composites Science and Technology*, vol 67, pp 1584-1600, 2007.
- [5] B. Madsen, A. Thygesen, H. Lilholt "Plant fibre composites – porosity and stiffness". *Composites Science and Technology*, vol 69, pp 1057-1069, 2009.

Fig. 6. Properties for cellulose fibres and their composites, potentials and obstacles.